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**INTRODUCTION TO THE COS
METHOD FOR OPTION
PRICING**

Autor: Guillem Navarra

Directors: Dr. Josep Vives, Dr. Jordi Vitrià

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Abstract

The main goal of this work is to introduce the COS method, a Fourier–cosine series based technique for the fast numerical pricing of financial options. We start from the basic financial and mathematical ideas needed to understand option pricing, including derivative contracts, risk-neutral valuation, the Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing, Brownian motion, and the Black-Scholes framework. After that, we introduce Fourier methods and explain why characteristic functions are useful when the distribution of the asset price is not handled directly.

The project then focuses on the derivation and implementation of the COS method. The method is presented through the truncation interval, the model characteristic function, the payoff coefficients, and the finite cosine sum. We apply it first to the Black-Scholes model, where a closed-form formula is available and can be used as a benchmark. Then we extend the numerical study to the Heston and Bates models, where the characteristic function approach is especially useful.

Finally, the method is implemented in Python and tested through several numerical experiments. The results show that the COS method achieves very high accuracy with a relatively small number of terms, while Monte Carlo simulation needs many more paths to reduce the error. This makes the COS method a powerful and efficient alternative for option pricing, especially in models where closed-form prices are not directly available.

Notation: Throughout this work, i denotes the imaginary unit, \mathbb{R} the real line, and FTAP the Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing. We write S_t for the price of the underlying asset at time t , S_0 for its initial value, S_T for its value at maturity, K for the strike price, and T for the time to maturity. The risk-free interest rate is denoted by r , the dividend yield by q , and the volatility by σ . Brownian motion is denoted by W_t .

When logarithmic variables are used in the COS method, we write

$$x = \log\left(\frac{S_0}{K}\right), \quad y = \log\left(\frac{S_T}{K}\right).$$

The characteristic function of the model is denoted by ϕ , and its Fourier variable is denoted by ω or u . The interval $[a, b]$ is the truncation interval used in the COS approximation, c_n denotes the cumulants of the log-price, and N is the number of terms in the finite cosine expansion. The payoff coefficients are denoted by V_k or U_k , depending on the notation used in the corresponding section.

Chapter 1

Financial and Mathematical Preliminaries

This project uses as source of information the standard introduction to financial derivatives and risk-neutral pricing in Neftci [1].

1.1 Financial derivatives and option contracts

A derivative is any financial instrument whose value depends on the price of another underlying asset. Among these instruments are the following (see [2]):

Forward contracts:

A forward is a contract between two parties by which both of them agree to buy or sell an amount of a given asset at a predetermined price on a future date. These contracts are private. Therefore, they are not traded on exchanges.

Futures contracts:

Futures are very similar to forwards. The only difference is that they are publicly traded because they take place through a liaison (the exchange), which makes sure everyone keeps their agreements.

Option contracts:

An option can be defined fairly simply: It is the right, but not the obligation, to buy or sell something at a predetermined price and, in some cases, at a predetermined time. In other words, an option lets you take the benefit from the upside of a forward contract, while avoiding the downside, and this flexibility costs a small fee.

Main types of option contracts (see [3]):

- **Call option contract:** In a call option transaction, a position is opened when one or more contracts are bought from the seller. The seller is paid a premium to assume the obligation of selling shares at the strike price. The position is called a covered call if the seller holds the shares to be sold.
- **Put option contract:** Buyers of put options often speculate on price declines in the underlying asset and own the right to sell the shares at the strike price. If the share price drops below the strike price before or at expiration, the buyer can sell the shares to the option seller at the strike price, or sell the contract if the shares are not held in the portfolio.

1.2 Risk-neutral pricing

The idea of risk-neutral pricing is fundamental in quantitative finance and derivative pricing. It allows us to value financial instruments as if investors were indifferent to risk. In this theoretical framework, the expected return on all assets is assumed to be the risk-free short-term interest rate. This simplifies the task of pricing a derivative by eliminating the need to estimate individual investor risk preferences or market risk premiums. Instead, the value of an asset is its expected value under a risk-neutral probability measure, discounted at the risk-free short-term interest rate. Risk-neutral pricing is a cornerstone of modern financial modeling, providing a consistent and arbitrage-free framework for valuation (see [4]).

For a derivative with payoff V_T at time T , its price V_0 at time $t = 0$ under risk-neutral pricing can be expressed as:

$$V_0 = e^{-rT} \mathbb{E}^Q[V_T].$$

Where:

- V_0 : Present value of the derivative at time 0.
- e : The base of the natural logarithm (approximately 2.71828).
- r : The continuously compounded risk-free short-term interest rate.
- T : Time to maturity of the derivative (in years).

- $\mathbb{E}^Q[\cdot]$: The expectation operator under the risk-neutral probability measure Q .
- V_T : The payoff of the derivative at maturity T .

Problems with this model

Problems with risk-free models:

1. **Continuous hedging:** This model assumes the possibility of continuously hedging positions to eliminate risk. This is impossible in practice due to transaction costs and liquidity constraints.
2. **Absence of arbitrage:** The model assumes that arbitrage is identified and exploited instantly, so that there are no market inefficiencies.
3. **Model risk:** The choice of model is a key element. If the model is not appropriate, the results will not be close to reality.
4. **Parameter estimation:** Inputs such as future volatility and interest rates must be estimated, and errors in these approximations can lead to pricing mismatches.

1.3 The Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing

The Fundamental Theorem of Asset Pricing connects the economic idea of no-arbitrage with a probabilistic representation of prices. In its standard form, it states that the absence of arbitrage is equivalent to the existence of a risk-neutral (equivalently, martingale) measure under which discounted asset prices evolve as martingales (see [5]).

Definitions

Let Ω be a finite set containing all possible outcomes of a process. For us, E will be \mathbb{R} , \mathbb{R}^d with $d \geq 1$, or a similar Euclidean space.

Sigma algebras and filtrations

Definition 1.1. A σ -algebra on Ω is a collection \mathcal{G} of subsets of Ω such that $\emptyset, \Omega \in \mathcal{G}$, $A^c \in \mathcal{G}$ whenever $A \in \mathcal{G}$, and $\bigcup_{i=1}^{\infty} A_i \in \mathcal{G}$ whenever $A_i \in \mathcal{G}$ for every $i \geq 1$.

Example 1.2. Let us think of a coin-flip process with N flips, where H denotes heads and T denotes tails. This will help us understand the concept of filtration (see [7]).

At time $t = 0$, we have the trivial σ -algebra

$$\mathcal{F}_0 = \{\emptyset, \Omega\},$$

and we do not know what the outcome of the process will be at $t = N$.

At time $t = 1$, let A_H be the set of processes starting with $H \dots$ and let A_T be the set of processes starting with $T \dots$. We then set

$$\mathcal{F}_1 = \sigma(A_H, A_T).$$

At time $t = 2$, let A_{HH} , A_{HT} , A_{TH} and A_{TT} be the sets of processes starting with

$$HH\dots, HT\dots, TH\dots, TT\dots,$$

and we set

$$\mathcal{F}_2 = \sigma(A_{HH}, A_{HT}, A_{TH}, A_{TT}).$$

At time $t = N$, we end up with the finest information and

$$\mathcal{F}_N = 2^\Omega.$$

An intuitive picture of the atoms of the σ -algebras in a filtration for an N -step coin-flip process.

Definition 1.3. A *filtration* is a sequence of σ -algebras

$$\mathcal{F}_0, \mathcal{F}_1, \mathcal{F}_2, \dots, \mathcal{F}_N,$$

such that

$$\mathcal{F}_0 \subseteq \mathcal{F}_1 \subseteq \dots \subseteq \mathcal{F}_N.$$

Definition 1.4. Let $X : \Omega \rightarrow E$ be a function, and let \mathcal{G} be a σ -algebra on Ω . We say that X is \mathcal{G} -measurable if

$$X^{-1}(B) \in \mathcal{G}$$

for every Borel set $B \subseteq E$.

Definition 1.5. A *process* is a sequence of functions

$$X_0, X_1, \dots, X_N : \Omega \rightarrow E.$$

We will now denote a process by (X_n) and a filtration by (\mathcal{F}_n) .

Definition 1.6. Given a process (X_n) and a filtration (\mathcal{F}_n) , we will say that (X_n) is (\mathcal{F}_n) -*adapted* if X_n is \mathcal{F}_n -measurable $\forall n = 0, \dots, N$.

Assets, markets and strategies

Definition 1.7. Given $(\Omega, (\mathcal{F}_n))$, an *asset* is a positive real-valued, (\mathcal{F}_n) -adapted process.

Definition 1.8. A *market* is a finite set of assets S^0, \dots, S^d .

Definition 1.9. A *strategy* $(\Phi_n)_{n=0}^N = (\Phi_n^0, \Phi_n^1, \dots, \Phi_n^d)_{n=0}^N$ is an \mathbb{R}^{d+1} predictable process.

Definition 1.10. We say that a process is *predictable* if each Φ_n^j is \mathcal{F}_{n-1} -measurable.

Each Φ_n^j corresponds to an S^j in the market and quantifies the amount of that asset to be bought at time $n - 1$.

See that these concepts are defined for a strategy to be able to tell where to allocate assets before a given time. If not, this would not make sense.

Definition 1.11. The *value* of a strategy $V_n(\Phi)$ is just the sum of all assets held at a time times the price of those assets at that moment, or as a mathematical expression:

$$V_n(\Phi) = \sum_{i=0}^d \Phi_n^i \cdot S_n^i.$$

Or as the dot product

$$V_n(\Phi) = \Phi_n \cdot S_n.$$

Definition 1.12. We say that S^0 is a *riskless asset* if, at a given time n ,

$$S_n^0 = (1 + r)^n$$

for some risk-free short-term interest rate $r > 0$.

We use this riskless asset to deflate our strategy in order to compare it to a riskless benchmark (trivial strategy). In discrete time, we write the riskless asset with per-period compounding.

Definition 1.13. We call the *discounted value* of an asset S_n^i at a given time n

$$\tilde{S}_n^i = S_n^i \cdot \frac{1}{S_n^0}.$$

From now on, we will assume that (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) is a finite probability space.

Discounted value, self financing strategies and arbitrage

Definition 1.14. The *discounted value* of a strategy Φ is

$$\tilde{V}_n(\Phi) = V_n(\Phi) \cdot \frac{1}{S_n^0}.$$

Now we want to introduce the concept of self-financing strategies. Intuitively, this means that a strategy, when taking a particular position in the market, will only use the resources that it has available to it from making use of the assets that it already has in its portfolio.

Definition 1.15. We say that a strategy is *self-financing* if

$$V_n(\Phi) = \Phi_n \cdot S_n = \Phi_{n+1} \cdot S_n.$$

Where the last term is

$$\Phi_{n+1} \cdot S_n = \sum_{i=0}^d \Phi_{n+1}^i \cdot S_n^i.$$

This can be interpreted as the cost for a person to take a position following the strategy Φ at time n .

Note that if Φ is self-financing, then we can write the difference in the value of the portfolio from n to $n + 1$ as

$$\begin{aligned} V_{n+1} - V_n &= \Phi_{n+1} \cdot S_{n+1} - \Phi_n \cdot S_n \\ &= \Phi_{n+1} \cdot S_{n+1} - \Phi_{n+1} \cdot S_n \\ &= \Phi_{n+1} \cdot (S_{n+1} - S_n). \end{aligned}$$

That intuitively expresses the new positions taken in the market times the difference in value of the assets after they have updated.

Definition 1.16. A strategy Φ is *admissible* if Φ is self-financing.

Now let us discuss how this ties to arbitrage. In a very simple way, arbitrage is just getting something for nothing, but that will not let us study its properties and consequences, so we need a formal definition.

Definition 1.17. A strategy Φ is an *arbitrage strategy* if it is admissible,

$$\begin{aligned} V_0(\Phi) &= 0, \\ V_N(\Phi) &\geq 0 \quad \forall \omega \in \Omega, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$P(V_N(\Phi) > 0) > 0.$$

Definition 1.18. We say that a market is *viable* if it does not admit an arbitrage strategy.

Probability theory concepts and martingales

In this section we will get the last tools we need in order to enunciate the FTAP. They will come from probability theory. Note that our definitions will be done given that our space Ω is finite and all of our singletons are measurable.

Definition 1.19. Given a finite probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) , a sub- σ -algebra $\mathcal{G} \subseteq \mathcal{F}$, and a function $X : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, we define the *conditional expectation* of X relative to \mathcal{G} , denoted by $\mathbb{E}_P[X | \mathcal{G}]$, as the unique \mathcal{G} -measurable function $Y : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\sum_{\omega \in A} Y(\omega)P(\omega) = \sum_{\omega \in A} X(\omega)P(\omega) \quad \forall A \in \mathcal{G}.$$

Proposition 1.20. *The following properties hold:*

(i) $\mathbb{E}_P[X | \mathcal{G}]$ is \mathcal{G} -measurable.

(ii) If $A \in \mathcal{G}$, then

$$\sum_{\omega \in A} X(\omega)P(\omega) = \sum_{\omega \in A} \mathbb{E}_P[X | \mathcal{G}](\omega)P(\omega).$$

Definition 1.21. Assume given a finite probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) and a filtration $(\mathcal{F}_n)_{n=0}^N$. A process $(X_n)_{n=0}^N$ is a (\mathcal{F}_n) -martingale if (X_n) is (\mathcal{F}_n) -adapted and

$$\mathbb{E}_P[X_n | \mathcal{F}_{n-1}] = X_{n-1} \quad \forall n = 1, \dots, N.$$

The intuition for this is that, if one is trying to guess the value of X_n at time $n - 1$, then its expected value is the same as the value at time $n - 1$, X_{n-1} . Taken to stock prices, this means the following: if stock prices are martingales, given all the information that one has today, the stock price tomorrow is nothing more than the stock price today.

Definition 1.22. Two probability measures P and Q on Ω are *equivalent* if they have the same null sets; that is,

$$P(A) = 0 \iff Q(A) = 0$$

for every $A \subseteq \Omega$.

FTAP

Theorem 1.23. *A market $(\Omega, (\mathcal{F}_n), S^0, \dots, S^d)$ on a finite probability space (Ω, \mathcal{F}, P) is viable, that is, it admits no arbitrage strategy, if and only if there exists a probability measure Q on Ω equivalent to P such that the discounted prices are (\mathcal{F}_n) -martingales under Q .*

The following proof is based on [6].

Proof. First suppose that there exists a probability measure Q equivalent to P such that the discounted prices are (\mathcal{F}_n) -martingales under Q . Let Φ be an admissible strategy with $V_0(\Phi) = 0$. Since Φ is self-financing, the same computation as above with discounted prices gives

$$\tilde{V}_N(\Phi) = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^d \Phi_n^i (\tilde{S}_n^i - \tilde{S}_{n-1}^i).$$

Each Φ_n^i is \mathcal{F}_{n-1} -measurable, and (\tilde{S}_n^i) is a martingale under Q . Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}_Q \left[\Phi_n^i (\tilde{S}_n^i - \tilde{S}_{n-1}^i) \right] = 0,$$

and hence

$$\mathbb{E}_Q \left[\tilde{V}_N(\Phi) \right] = \mathbb{E}_Q \left[\tilde{V}_0(\Phi) \right] = V_0(\Phi) = 0.$$

Now, if Φ were an arbitrage strategy, then $\tilde{V}_N(\Phi) \geq 0$ for all $\omega \in \Omega$ and $\tilde{V}_N(\Phi) > 0$ with positive P -probability. Since Q is equivalent to P , this would also have positive Q -probability, so its expectation under Q would be strictly positive. This contradicts the equality above. Therefore, the market is viable.

Conversely, suppose that the market is viable. Since Ω is finite, write

$$\Omega = \{\omega_1, \dots, \omega_M\}.$$

We can identify random variables on Ω with vectors in \mathbb{R}^M . Let Γ be the set of random variables X such that $X(\omega) \geq 0$ for every $\omega \in \Omega$ and $X(\omega) > 0$ for at least one ω . Let

$$\mathcal{C} = \left\{ X \in \Gamma : \sum_{\omega \in \Omega} X(\omega) = 1 \right\}.$$

Also define

$$L = \left\{ \tilde{V}_N(\Phi) : \Phi \text{ is self-financing and } V_0(\Phi) = 0 \right\}.$$

The set L is a linear subspace of the random variables on Ω . Moreover, $L \cap \mathcal{C} = \emptyset$. Indeed, if some $X \in L \cap \mathcal{C}$ existed, then $X = \tilde{V}_N(\Phi)$ for a self-financing strategy

with initial value zero, and X would be non-negative everywhere and positive somewhere. This would be an arbitrage opportunity, contradicting viability.

By the separating hyperplane theorem, there exists a linear functional $\tilde{\zeta}$ such that

$$\tilde{\zeta}(X) > 0 \quad \forall X \in \mathcal{C}, \quad \tilde{\zeta}(Y) = 0 \quad \forall Y \in L.$$

Writing

$$\tilde{\zeta}(X) = \sum_{j=1}^M \lambda_j X(\omega_j),$$

we get $\lambda_j > 0$ for every j , because the random variable which is equal to 1 at ω_j and zero elsewhere belongs to \mathcal{C} . Define

$$Q(\omega_j) = \frac{\lambda_j}{\sum_{k=1}^M \lambda_k}, \quad j = 1, \dots, M.$$

Then $Q(\omega_j) > 0$ for every j , so Q is equivalent to P .

It remains to show that the discounted prices are martingales under Q . Take any asset $i \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ and any predictable process Φ^i . Consider the strategy that holds Φ_n^i units of asset i at time n and no units of the other risky assets, choosing the position in the riskless asset so that it is self-financing and has initial value zero. By self-financing, its terminal discounted value satisfies

$$\tilde{V}_N(\Phi) = \sum_{n=1}^N \Phi_n^i (\tilde{S}_n^i - \tilde{S}_{n-1}^i) \in L.$$

Therefore,

$$\mathbb{E}_Q \left[\sum_{n=1}^N \Phi_n^i (\tilde{S}_n^i - \tilde{S}_{n-1}^i) \right] = 0.$$

Now choose $\Phi_n^i = \mathbf{1}_A$ for some $A \in \mathcal{F}_{n-1}$ and $\Phi_l^i = 0$ for $l \neq n$. Then

$$\mathbb{E}_Q \left[\mathbf{1}_A (\tilde{S}_n^i - \tilde{S}_{n-1}^i) \right] = 0 \quad \forall A \in \mathcal{F}_{n-1}.$$

This is exactly the conditional expectation condition

$$\mathbb{E}_Q \left[\tilde{S}_n^i \mid \mathcal{F}_{n-1} \right] = \tilde{S}_{n-1}^i.$$

Hence every discounted price process is a martingale under Q , and the theorem follows. \square

1.4 Stochastic processes and the Black-Scholes model

This section gives the continuous-time counterpart of some of the discrete-time notions above. The continuous-time background on Brownian motion and the Black-Scholes model can be found in [8] and [9]. Unlike the previous section, we are no longer working on a finite probability space, but in a continuous-time setting driven by Brownian motion. To keep notation consistent with Chapter 1, a continuous-time filtration will be denoted by $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t \geq 0}$ and a continuous-time process by $(X_t)_{t \geq 0}$. We extend the notions of process and adaptedness from Section 1.3 to continuous time. We also keep the option terminology introduced in Section 1.1; in particular, we denote the exercise price by K .

1.4.1 Definitions

Definition 1.24. A *continuous-time filtration* is a family of σ -algebras $(\mathcal{F}_t)_{t \geq 0}$ such that

$$\mathcal{F}_s \subseteq \mathcal{F}_t$$

whenever $0 \leq s \leq t$.

Definition 1.25. A *standard Brownian motion* (Wiener process) is an (\mathcal{F}_t) -adapted process $(W_t)_{t \geq 0}$ with the following properties:

- (1) $W_0 = 0$.
- (2) The process $(W_t)_{t \geq 0}$ has stationary, independent increments.
- (3) The increment $W_{t+s} - W_s$ has the Normal(0, t) distribution.

Definition 1.26. An *Itô process* is an (\mathcal{F}_t) -adapted process $(X_t)_{t \geq 0}$ that satisfies

$$dX_t = a(t, X_t) dt + b(t, X_t) dW_t,$$

where $(W_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is a standard Brownian motion.

Definition 1.27. Under the risk-neutral measure, in the Black-Scholes model the stock-price process $(S_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is modeled by the stochastic differential equation

$$dS_t = rS_t dt + \sigma S_t dW_t, \quad S_0 > 0,$$

and the riskless asset satisfies

$$S_t^0 = e^{rt},$$

where r is the risk-free short-term interest rate.

In continuous time, we write the riskless asset with continuous compounding.

Definition 1.28. If a random variable Y follows the normal distribution with mean μ and variance σ^2 , then $Z = e^Y$ follows the *log-normal distribution*. We denote by $N(x)$ the cumulative distribution function of a standard normal random variable.

1.4.2 Main results

Theorem 1.29 (Black-Scholes Formula). *The value of a European call option (C_0) can be calculated given its stock price (S_0), exercise price (K), time to expiration (T), standard deviation of log returns (σ), and risk-free short-term interest rate (r). Assume that the option satisfies the following conditions:*

- (a) *The short-term interest rate is known and is constant through time.*
- (b) *The stock price follows a random walk in continuous time with a variance rate proportional to the square of the stock price. Thus the distribution of possible stock prices at the end of any finite interval is log-normal. The variance rate of the return on the stock is constant.*
- (c) *The stock pays no dividends or other distributions.*
- (d) *The option is European, that is, it can only be exercised at maturity.*
- (e) *There are no transaction costs in buying or selling the stock or the option.*
- (f) *It is possible to borrow any fraction of the price of a security to buy it or to hold it, at the short-term interest rate.*
- (g) *There are no penalties to short selling. A seller who does not own a security will simply accept the price of the security from a buyer, and will agree to settle with the buyer on some future date by paying him an amount equal to the price of the security on that date.*

Then, the price can be calculated by

$$C_0 = S_0 N(d_1) - Ke^{-rT} N(d_2),$$

where

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{S_0}{K}\right) + \left(r + \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) T}{\sigma\sqrt{T}}, \quad d_2 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{S_0}{K}\right) + \left(r - \frac{\sigma^2}{2}\right) T}{\sigma\sqrt{T}}.$$

Theorem 1.30 (Black-Scholes Equation). *Let $(S_t)_{t \geq 0}$ be the stock-price process and let the value of an option at time t be $f(t, S_t)$, let the standard deviation of stock returns be σ , and let the risk-free short-term interest rate be r . Then the price of an option over time can be expressed by the following partial differential equation:*

$$\frac{\partial f(t, S_t)}{\partial t} + rS_t \frac{\partial f(t, S_t)}{\partial S_t} + \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 S_t^2 \frac{\partial^2 f(t, S_t)}{\partial S_t^2} = rf(t, S_t).$$

Remark 1.31. The proofs are omitted here and can be found in [9].

Example 1.32. Let us try finding the price of a European call option whose stock price is \$90, months to expiration is 6 months, risk-free short-term interest rate is 8%, standard deviation of stock is 23%, and exercise price is \$80.

Since $S_0 = 90$, $T = 0.5$, $r = 0.08$, $\sigma = 0.23$, and $K = 80$, plug in those values into the Black-Scholes formula to get

$$C_0 = 90N(d_1) - 80e^{-0.08 \cdot 0.5}N(d_2),$$

where

$$d_1 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{90}{80}\right) + \left(0.08 + \frac{0.23^2}{2}\right)0.5}{0.23\sqrt{0.5}} = 1.0515$$

and

$$d_2 = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{90}{80}\right) + \left(0.08 - \frac{0.23^2}{2}\right)0.5}{0.23\sqrt{0.5}} = 0.8889.$$

Now, use the normal distribution table to find

$$N(1.0515) = 0.8535, \quad N(0.8889) = 0.813.$$

Therefore, the value of the option is

$$C_0 = 90 \cdot 0.8535 - 80 \cdot e^{-0.08 \cdot 0.5} \cdot 0.813 = 14.33.$$

1.5 Beyond Black-Scholes: Heston and Bates models

In 1993, Steven L. Heston proposed a volatility model where the price of the underlying asset $(S_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is characterized by the following risk-neutral dynamics (see [10]). The presentation below also follows [11] and [12].

Theorem 1.33 (Heston model). *Let $(S_t)_{t \geq 0}$ be the price process of an asset, and let $(v_t)_{t \geq 0}$ be its instantaneous variance process, so that $\sqrt{v_t}$ is the volatility. Let $(W_t^S)_{t \geq 0}$ and $(W_t^V)_{t \geq 0}$ be Brownian motions with correlation ρ . Let v_0 be the initial variance, let θ be the long-run average variance of the price, let κ be the rate at which v_t reverts to θ , let ξ be the volatility of the volatility, which determines the variance of v_t , and let r be the risk-free short-term interest rate. Then*

$$dS_t = rS_t dt + \sqrt{v_t}S_t dW_t^S,$$

$$dv_t = \kappa(\theta - v_t) dt + \xi\sqrt{v_t} dW_t^V.$$

Theorem 1.34 (Bates model). *The Bates model assumes that the stock-price process $(S_t)_{t \geq 0}$ has risk-neutral dynamics given by*

$$\frac{dS_t}{S_t} = (r - q - \lambda(\bar{\alpha} - 1)) dt + \sqrt{v_t} dW_t^S + (\alpha_t - 1) dN_t,$$

$$dv_t = \kappa(\theta - v_t) dt + \zeta \sqrt{v_t} dW_t^v,$$

where $(N_t)_{t \geq 0}$ is a Poisson process with intensity λ , α_t is log-normally distributed with $\mathbb{E}_{t-}^{\mathbb{Q}}[\alpha_t] = \bar{\alpha}$, and q is the dividend yield. In other words, the Bates model is the Heston model with independent jumps added to the stock-price dynamics. This independence implies that the characteristic function of the log-stock price can also be computed once it is known for the Heston model (see [13]).

Chapter 2

Fourier Analysis and Characteristic Functions

This chapter is intended to give the reader a first glance at the properties and usage of Fourier analysis in option pricing. It also explains how this is deeply tied to characteristic functions and density recovery. One can think of this chapter as a brief introduction that prepares the reader to understand the derivation and implementation of the COS method.

2.1 The Fourier transform and its properties

In this chapter we introduce the Fourier transform because it is one of the main tools behind transform-based option pricing methods. In the models we have discussed so far, the probability density of the log-price is often not available in closed form, while its Fourier transform, that is, the characteristic function, is frequently known explicitly. This makes it possible to move the pricing problem to the Fourier domain and recover option values efficiently by numerical integration. The COS method is based on this same idea, and in particular on the close relation between the characteristic function and the coefficients of a Fourier-cosine expansion of the density (see [14]).

Definition 2.1. We denote by $\mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ the *Schwartz space* on \mathbb{R} . This is the space of smooth functions whose derivatives decrease faster than any inverse polynomial at infinity. The Fourier transform of a function $f \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ is defined by

$$\widehat{f}(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x) e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx.$$

Some simple properties of the Fourier transform are gathered in the following

proposition. We use the notation

$$f(x) \longrightarrow \widehat{f}(\xi)$$

to mean that \widehat{f} denotes the Fourier transform of f .

Proposition 2.2. *If $f \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$ then:*

- (i) $f(x+h) \longrightarrow \widehat{f}(\xi)e^{2\pi i h \xi}$ whenever $h \in \mathbb{R}$.
- (ii) $f(x)e^{-2\pi i x h} \longrightarrow \widehat{f}(\xi+h)$ whenever $h \in \mathbb{R}$.
- (iii) $f(\delta x) \longrightarrow \delta^{-1}\widehat{f}(\delta^{-1}\xi)$ whenever $\delta > 0$.
- (iv) $f'(x) \longrightarrow 2\pi i \xi \widehat{f}(\xi)$.
- (v) $-2\pi i x f(x) \longrightarrow \frac{d}{d\xi} \widehat{f}(\xi)$.

Remark 2.3. The following proof follows Stein and Shakarchi [18].

Proof. Let

$$\widehat{f}(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx.$$

Since $f \in \mathcal{S}(\mathbb{R})$, the changes of variables, integration by parts, and differentiation under the integral sign used below are justified.

For (i), set $y = x + h$. Then

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x+h)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y)e^{-2\pi i (y-h)\xi} dy = e^{2\pi i h \xi} \widehat{f}(\xi).$$

For (ii),

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)e^{-2\pi i x h} e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)e^{-2\pi i x (\xi+h)} dx = \widehat{f}(\xi+h).$$

For (iii), set $y = \delta x$. Since $\delta > 0$,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(\delta x)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx = \delta^{-1} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(y)e^{-2\pi i y (\delta^{-1}\xi)} dy = \delta^{-1} \widehat{f}(\delta^{-1}\xi).$$

For (iv), integration by parts gives

$$\widehat{f}'(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f'(x)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx = 2\pi i \xi \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx = 2\pi i \xi \widehat{f}(\xi),$$

because the boundary term vanishes. Finally, for (v),

$$\frac{d}{d\xi} \widehat{f}(\xi) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x)(-2\pi i x)e^{-2\pi i x \xi} dx,$$

which is exactly the Fourier transform of $-2\pi i x f(x)$. □

2.2 Characteristic functions of asset log-returns

In this section we develop analytic expressions for the Fourier transform of an option price. These Fourier transforms are expressed in terms of the characteristic function of the log price (see [15]).

Definition 2.4. Consider a European call option of maturity T , written on the terminal spot price S_T of an underlying asset. If we write

$$s_T = \ln(S_T),$$

then the *characteristic function* of s_T is defined by

$$\phi_T(u) = \mathbb{E} \left[e^{i u s_T} \right].$$

In many models used in option pricing, the density of the log-price is difficult to compute explicitly, while its characteristic function is available in closed form. This is one of the main reasons Fourier methods are useful in mathematical finance. In our case, this point is especially relevant because the COS method also starts from the characteristic function of the log-price and uses it to recover option values efficiently (see [14], [15]).

Let $k = \ln(K)$ denote the log-strike, and let $C_T(k)$ be the time-0 value of a call option with maturity T and strike $K = e^k$. If $q_T(s)$ denotes the risk-neutral density of the log-price s_T , then

$$\phi_T(u) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i u s} q_T(s) ds,$$

and the call value can be written as

$$C_T(k) = \int_k^{\infty} e^{-rT} (e^s - e^k) q_T(s) ds.$$

Observe that $C_T(k) \rightarrow S_0$ as $k \rightarrow -\infty$, so the call-pricing function is not square-integrable. For this reason, Carr and Madan introduce the *modified call price*

$$c_T(k) = e^{\alpha k} C_T(k),$$

for $\alpha > 0$, and then consider its Fourier transform

$$\psi_T(v) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i v k} c_T(k) dk.$$

Remark 2.5. The role of this modification is to obtain a function with better integrability properties in the log-strike variable. In the Carr–Madan approach this makes it possible to apply the FFT to recover option prices numerically. In our

work, the same characteristic-function point of view will be used later in a different way: instead of pricing through the FFT, the COS method reconstructs the density by a Fourier-cosine expansion and then computes the option value from that expansion (see [14], [15]).

2.3 Density recovery via the Gil-Pelaez inversion formula

The Gil–Pelaez inversion formula is a Fourier-analytic technique for recovering the cumulative distribution function and the probability density function of a real-valued random variable from its characteristic function. In practical terms, it allows us to pass from the characteristic function, which is often easier to compute, to direct expressions for the distribution function. This fits naturally with our work, because in option pricing models such as Black-Scholes, Heston, and Bates, the characteristic function of the log-price is often known explicitly, while the density is not. Since the COS method is also built from the characteristic function of the log-price, this inversion point of view helps explain why Fourier-based pricing methods are effective in our setting (see [14], [16]).

Proposition 2.6. *Let $s_T = \ln(S_T)$ be the log-price at maturity T , let*

$$\phi_T(u) = \mathbb{E} \left[e^{ius_T} \right]$$

be its characteristic function, and let

$$F_T(x) = \mathbb{P}(s_T \leq x)$$

be its cumulative distribution function. If ϕ_T is absolutely integrable on \mathbb{R} , then at every continuity point x of F_T the Gil–Pelaez inversion formulas give

$$q_T(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Re \left(e^{-iux} \phi_T(u) \right) du$$

for the density q_T of s_T , and

$$F_T(x) = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\infty \Im \left(\frac{e^{-iux} \phi_T(u)}{u} \right) du.$$

Here, $\Re(z)$ and $\Im(z)$ denote the real and imaginary parts of a complex number z (see [16]).

These formulas arise from the classical Fourier inversion formula

$$q_T(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^\infty e^{-iux} \phi_T(u) du.$$

By splitting the integral over the positive and negative half-lines and using the Hermitian symmetry

$$\phi_T(-u) = \overline{\phi_T(u)},$$

one obtains real-valued integrals over $u > 0$. This is useful numerically, since it replaces an oscillatory integral over the whole real line by expressions that are better suited to computation (see [16]).

Remark 2.7. For our purposes, the importance of the Gil–Pelaez inversion formula is that it provides a direct way to recover the density or distribution of the log-price once its characteristic function is known. This is closely related to the point of view of the COS method developed later in this work: there too, the characteristic function is the main analytic input, and the option price is obtained after reconstructing distributional information from it (see [14], [16]).

Chapter 3

The COS Method

The aim of this chapter is to apply what has been presented so far in order to give the reader the steps followed to derive the COS method. This chapter will be heavily influenced by the original paper *A Novel Pricing Method for European Options Based on Fourier-Cosine Series Expansions*, by Fang and Oosterlee. For further details on the introduction or extra layers on what will be stated here, feel free to visit the paper (see [14]).

We will start by deriving the COS method from what we have already seen. Then, we will talk about Fourier-cosine coefficients of the payoff function and their importance for the COS method. Lastly, we will analyse its convergence and see how errors are computed.

3.1 Derivation of the COS pricing formula

The point of departure for pricing European options with numerical integration techniques is the risk-neutral valuation formula. If $v(x, t_0)$ denotes the option value at time t_0 , where x is the state variable at time t_0 , and y is the state variable at maturity T , then, following Fang and Oosterlee [14],

$$v(x, t_0) = e^{-r\Delta t} \mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}} [v(y, T) | x] = e^{-r\Delta t} \int_{\mathbb{R}} v(y, T) f(y|x) dy, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta t = T - t_0$, $\mathbb{E}^{\mathbb{Q}}[\cdot]$ is the expectation operator under the risk-neutral measure \mathbb{Q} , $f(y|x)$ denotes the conditional density of y given x , and r is the risk-free short-term interest rate.

In the Carr–Madan approach and its variants, the Fourier transform of a version of (1) is taken with respect to the log-strike. This requires damping of the payoff,

since for example a call option is not L^1 -integrable with respect to the logarithm of the strike. The resulting integral is available in closed form in Fourier space, and one then has to return to the original domain by numerically computing the inverse Fourier integral. In that step the FFT algorithm is appropriate (see [14], [15]).

Another Fourier-based pricing method that is relevant here is the CONV method. The main idea is to rewrite the risk-neutral valuation formula in a form that can be treated efficiently with the FFT, so it belongs to the same general family of transform methods as the ones we are discussing (see [14]).

The range of applications of numerical integration methods in finance has increased with efficient techniques for options with early exercise features. In particular, the CONV method is also based on the FFT algorithm and can be used efficiently for European options. The main difference with the Carr–Madan approach is that the transform is taken with respect to the log-spot price instead of the log-strike (see [14]).

These numerical integration methods have to solve certain forward or inverse Fourier integrals. In our setting, the density and its characteristic function form a Fourier pair:

$$\phi(\omega; x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{i\omega y} f(y|x) dy, \quad (2)$$

$$f(y|x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{-i\omega y} \phi(\omega; x) d\omega. \quad (3)$$

Fourier-cosine series expansions usually give an optimal approximation of functions with a finite support. For a function supported on $[0, \pi]$, the cosine expansion reads

$$f(\theta) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} 'A_k \cos(k\theta), \quad A_k = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^{\pi} f(\theta) \cos(k\theta) d\theta, \quad (4)$$

where ' indicates that the first term of the sum is divided by 2 (see [14]).

If one has any other function defined on a real finite interval $[a, b]$, then the change of variables

$$\theta := \frac{x-a}{b-a}\pi, \quad x = \frac{b-a}{\pi}\theta + a$$

can be used to perform the Fourier-cosine series expansion. It then reads

$$f(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} 'A_k \cos\left(k\pi \frac{x-a}{b-a}\right), \quad (5)$$

with

$$A_k = \frac{2}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) \cos\left(k\pi \frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) dx. \quad (6)$$

This is the form used by Fang and Oosterlee [14].

Now, we know that these functions have a cosine expansion. That means that we can start deriving the formula by truncating the infinite range of integration seen in the expression of the characteristic function (2). Using the conditions for the existence of the Fourier transform, the integrands in that equation approach zero at $\pm\infty$. That implies that we can truncate the integration range without losing a lot of accuracy. Let us suppose that we choose $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$ so that

$$\phi_1(\omega; x) := \int_a^b e^{i\omega y} f(y|x) dy \approx \int_{\mathbb{R}} e^{i\omega y} f(y|x) dy = \phi(\omega; x). \quad (7)$$

Comparing (7) with the cosine series coefficients of $f(x)$ on $[a, b]$ in (6), we see that

$$A_k(x) = \frac{2}{b-a} \Re \left\{ \phi_1 \left(\frac{k\pi}{b-a}; x \right) \exp \left(-i \frac{ka\pi}{b-a} \right) \right\}, \quad (8)$$

where $\Re\{\cdot\}$ denotes the real part. It then follows from (7) that $A_k(x) \approx F_k(x)$ with

$$F_k(x) = \frac{2}{b-a} \Re \left\{ \phi \left(\frac{k\pi}{b-a}; x \right) \exp \left(-i \frac{ka\pi}{b-a} \right) \right\}. \quad (9)$$

We now replace A_k by F_k in the series expansion of $f(x)$ on $[a, b]$, i.e.

$$f_1(y|x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} 'F_k(x) \cos \left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a} \right), \quad (10)$$

and truncate the series summation such that

$$f_2(y|x) = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} 'F_k(x) \cos \left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a} \right). \quad (11)$$

Since we know from [17] that the cosine series expansion of entire functions exhibits an exponential convergence, we can expect high accuracy from (11) for those functions with no singularities and low values of N . An exhaustive analysis on this will be done in further chapters.

3.1.1 Pricing European Options

We can now go back to the valuation formula and truncate the integration range to $[a, b] \subset \mathbb{R}$ to get our first approximation v_1 :

$$v_1(x, t_0) = e^{-r\Delta t} \int_a^b v(y, T) f(y|x) dy. \quad (12)$$

Since $f(y|x)$ is usually not known whereas the characteristic function is, we replace the density by its cosine expansion in y ,

$$f(y|x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} 'A_k(x) \cos\left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a}\right), \quad (13)$$

with

$$A_k(x) := \frac{2}{b-a} \int_a^b f(y|x) \cos\left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a}\right) dy. \quad (14)$$

So that

$$v_1(x, t_0) = e^{-r\Delta t} \int_a^b v(y, T) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} 'A_k(x) \cos\left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a}\right) dy. \quad (15)$$

We interchange the summation and integration, and insert the definition

$$V_k := \frac{2}{b-a} \int_a^b v(y, T) \cos\left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a}\right) dy, \quad (16)$$

resulting in

$$v_1(x, t_0) = \frac{1}{2}(b-a)e^{-r\Delta t} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} 'A_k(x) V_k. \quad (17)$$

Note that the V_k are precisely the Fourier-cosine coefficients of $v(y, T)$ with respect to y . Therefore, from (12) to (17), the original pricing expression has been rewritten in terms of the Fourier-cosine coefficients of the two real functions $f(y|x)$ and $v(y, T)$.

Since these coefficients decay rapidly, it is natural to truncate the series once more and define a second approximation v_2 :

$$v_2(x, t_0) = \frac{1}{2}(b-a)e^{-r\Delta t} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} 'A_k(x) V_k. \quad (18)$$

Also, as we saw before, the coefficients $A_k(x)$ defined in (14) can be approximated by $F_k(x)$ as defined in (9). If we replace $A_k(x)$ in (18) by $F_k(x)$, then we arrive at

$$v(x, t_0) \approx v_3(x, t_0) = e^{-r\Delta t} \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} ' \Re \left\{ \phi\left(\frac{k\pi}{b-a}; x\right) e^{-i\frac{ka\pi}{b-a}} \right\} V_k, \quad (19)$$

which is the COS formula for general underlying processes.

Later on, we will see that the V_k can be computed analytically for plain vanilla options. We will also see that (19) simplifies for the Lévy and Heston models, which makes it possible to handle many strikes at the same time (see [14]).

3.2 Fourier-cosine coefficients of the payoff function

Now only one step remains until we can use (19) as a pricing formula. We need to recover the values V_k , which can be done analytically.

We will start by assuming that the characteristic function of the log-asset price is known. Therefore, we represent the payoff as a function of the log-asset price. We denote the log-asset prices by

$$x := \ln\left(\frac{S_0}{K}\right) \quad \text{and} \quad y := \ln\left(\frac{S_T}{K}\right), \quad (20)$$

being S_t the underlying price at time t and K the strike price.

The payoff in log-asset price for European options is as follows:

$$v(y, T) \equiv [\alpha \cdot K(e^y - 1)]^+ \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for a call,} \\ -1 & \text{for a put.} \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

Now, we need a couple of mathematical results in order to derive V_k from its definition in (16).

Proposition 3.1. *The cosine series coefficients χ_k of $g(y) = e^y$ on $[c, d] \subset [a, b]$ and the cosine series coefficients ψ_k of $g(y) = 1$ on $[c, d] \subset [a, b]$, given by*

$$\chi_k(c, d) := \int_c^d e^y \cos\left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a}\right) dy, \quad (22)$$

and

$$\psi_k(c, d) := \int_c^d \cos\left(k\pi \frac{y-a}{b-a}\right) dy, \quad (23)$$

are known analytically.

Remark 3.2. The proof of this result can be found in Fang and Oosterlee's paper (see [14]).

In fact, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \chi_k(c, d) := & \frac{1}{1 + \left(\frac{k\pi}{b-a}\right)^2} \left[\cos\left(k\pi \frac{d-a}{b-a}\right) e^d - \cos\left(k\pi \frac{c-a}{b-a}\right) e^c \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{k\pi}{b-a} \sin\left(k\pi \frac{d-a}{b-a}\right) e^d - \frac{k\pi}{b-a} \sin\left(k\pi \frac{c-a}{b-a}\right) e^c \right], \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

and

$$\psi_k(c, d) := \begin{cases} \left[\sin\left(k\pi\frac{d-a}{b-a}\right) - \sin\left(k\pi\frac{c-a}{b-a}\right) \right] \frac{b-a}{k\pi}, & k \neq 0, \\ d - c, & k = 0. \end{cases} \quad (25)$$

Now, if one wants to get the values V_k for a call, it is enough to do

$$\begin{aligned} V_k^{\text{call}} &= \frac{2}{b-a} \int_0^b K(e^y - 1) \cos\left(k\pi\frac{y-a}{b-a}\right) dy \\ &= \frac{2}{b-a} K(\chi_k(0, b) - \psi_k(0, b)), \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

where χ_k and ψ_k are given by (24) and (25), respectively. Similarly, for a vanilla put, we find

$$V_k^{\text{put}} = \frac{2}{b-a} K(-\chi_k(a, 0) + \psi_k(a, 0)). \quad (27)$$

This gives us the values of V_k analytically, and so we can insert them directly into the COS pricing formula.

3.3 Error and convergence analysis

Fang and Oosterlee conclude their error analysis by observing that, in the derivation of the COS formula, there are three steps where an error is introduced: the truncation of the integration range, the truncation of the cosine series, and the replacement of the exact coefficients by their characteristic-function approximation. Therefore, the total error is split into three parts (see [14]):

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3, \quad (28)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 &:= v(x, t_0) - v_1(x, t_0), \\ \varepsilon_2 &:= v_1(x, t_0) - v_2(x, t_0), \\ \varepsilon_3 &:= v_2(x, t_0) - v_3(x, t_0). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

In our notation, the first two terms are

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_1 &= e^{-r\Delta t} \int_{\mathbb{R} \setminus [a, b]} v(y, T) f(y|x) dy, \\ \varepsilon_2 &= \frac{1}{2}(b-a)e^{-r\Delta t} \sum_{k=N}^{\infty} 'A_k(x) V_k. \end{aligned} \quad (30)$$

The key point is that ε_3 can also be bounded by truncation-range terms, so if $[a, b]$ is chosen large enough, then the dominant contribution comes from ε_2 . This is

why the decay of the cosine coefficients is the main ingredient in the analysis. If the density is smooth on $[a, b]$, then the cosine expansion converges exponentially. If the density has a discontinuity in one of its derivatives, the convergence becomes algebraic (see [14], [17]).

Proposition 3.3. *With a sufficiently large truncation range, the overall error satisfies an exponential bound*

$$|\varepsilon| < 2|\varepsilon_1| + Q|\varepsilon_4| + Pe^{-(N-1)v}, \quad (31)$$

when the density belongs to $C^\infty([a, b])$, where $\varepsilon_4 := \int_{\mathbb{R} \setminus [a, b]} f(y|x) dy$ and $P, Q, v > 0$ are constants. If the density has a discontinuity in one of its derivatives, then the error is only algebraic:

$$|\varepsilon| < 2|\varepsilon_1| + Q|\varepsilon_4| + \frac{\bar{P}}{(N-1)^{\beta-1}}, \quad (32)$$

for some constants $\bar{P} > 0$ and $\beta \geq 1$.

Proof. The proof follows the error analysis of Fang and Oosterlee (see [14]). From the decomposition

$$\varepsilon = \varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3,$$

we have

$$|\varepsilon| \leq |\varepsilon_1| + |\varepsilon_2| + |\varepsilon_3|.$$

If $[a, b]$ is sufficiently large, the coefficient-replacement error can be bounded by the truncation terms, so that

$$|\varepsilon_3| \leq |\varepsilon_1| + Q|\varepsilon_4|.$$

Therefore

$$|\varepsilon| \leq 2|\varepsilon_1| + Q|\varepsilon_4| + |\varepsilon_2|.$$

It remains to bound the tail ε_2 of the cosine expansion. If the density is in $C^\infty([a, b])$, the cosine coefficients decay exponentially, so

$$|\varepsilon_2| < Pe^{-(N-1)v}.$$

If the density has a discontinuity in one of its derivatives, the decay becomes algebraic, and

$$|\varepsilon_2| < \frac{\bar{P}}{(N-1)^{\beta-1}}.$$

Substituting these two possible bounds for $|\varepsilon_2|$ gives (31) and (32). \square

So, the practical conclusion is simple: once the truncation range is chosen well, the speed of convergence mainly depends on how smooth the density is on $[a, b]$.

Chapter 4

Implementation

4.1 Algorithm description and pseudocode

As seen in Fang and Oosterlee's paper, the implementation of the COS method mainly needs the following ingredients (see [14]):

- the truncation interval;
- the model characteristic function;
- the payoff coefficients V_k or U_k ;
- the finite cosine sum.

Fang and Oosterlee use the following truncation rule:

$$[a, b] = \left[c_1 - L\sqrt{c_2 + \sqrt{c_4}}, c_1 + L\sqrt{c_2 + \sqrt{c_4}} \right], \quad (4.1)$$

where c_n are the cumulants of $\ln(S_T/K)$ and $L = 10$.

The characteristic function to be used will be

$$\phi(\omega; x) = \mathbb{E} \left[e^{i\omega y} \mid x \right], \quad (4.2)$$

where ω is the Fourier variable, $x = \ln(S_0/K)$ is the state variable at the initial time, and $y = \ln(S_T/K)$ is the state variable at maturity.

The payoff coefficients will be computed analytically by integrating the payoff against the cosine basis on $[a, b]$, as in (16). For plain vanilla calls and puts, this integral can be written in terms of the functions χ_k and ψ_k , giving the formulas

(26) and (27).

Finally, the option value comes from the finite cosine sum of N terms. In the notation of the previous chapter, this is the approximation (19).

Therefore, the implementation can be summarized as follows:

- (1) Fix the model parameters, the option parameters, the number of terms N , and the value of L .
- (2) Compute the cumulants c_n and use (4.1) to obtain the interval $[a, b]$.
- (3) Set $x = \ln(S_0/K)$ and define

$$u_k = \frac{k\pi}{b-a}, \quad k = 0, \dots, N-1.$$

- (4) Compute the payoff coefficients V_k or U_k .
- (5) Evaluate the characteristic function of the chosen model at the points u_k .
- (6) Insert these quantities into the finite COS sum.

This is the main computational advantage of the method: once the payoff coefficients and the truncation range are fixed, changing from one model to another mainly means changing the characteristic function.

4.2 European options under the Black-Scholes model

Let

$$x = \ln\left(\frac{S_0}{K}\right), \quad y = \ln\left(\frac{S_T}{K}\right),$$

where S_0 is the initial price of the underlying asset, S_T is the price of the underlying asset at maturity, and K is the strike price.

Under the Black-Scholes model, we know that

$$y = x + \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)T + \sigma W_T.$$

That gives the characteristic function for Black-Scholes:

$$\phi_{\text{BS}}(\omega; x) = \exp\left(i\omega\left(x + \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)T\right) - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\omega^2T\right).$$

For this model we choose

$$c_1 = x + \left(r - \frac{1}{2}\sigma^2\right)T, \quad c_2 = \sigma^2T, \quad c_4 = 0.$$

4.3 European options under the Heston and Bates models

For the Heston model, the characteristic function is the following (see [14]):

$$\phi_{\text{H}}(\omega; x, \nu_0) = \phi_{\text{H}}(\omega; \nu_0) e^{i\omega x},$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{\text{H}}(\omega; \nu_0) = & \exp \left(i\omega r T + \frac{\nu_0}{\xi^2} \left(\frac{1 - e^{-DT}}{1 - Ge^{-DT}} \right) (\kappa - i\rho\xi\omega - D) \right) \\ & \times \exp \left(\frac{\kappa\theta}{\xi^2} \left[T(\kappa - i\rho\xi\omega - D) - 2 \log \left(\frac{1 - Ge^{-DT}}{1 - G} \right) \right] \right), \end{aligned}$$

with

$$D = \sqrt{(\kappa - i\rho\xi\omega)^2 + \xi^2(\omega^2 + i\omega)}, \quad G = \frac{\kappa - i\rho\xi\omega - D}{\kappa - i\rho\xi\omega + D}.$$

For the Bates model, the characteristic function is obtained by multiplying the Heston characteristic function by the jump component (see [13]):

$$\phi_{\text{Bates}}(\omega; x, \nu_0) = \phi_{\text{H}}(\omega; x, \nu_0) \exp \left(-i\omega q T + \lambda T \left(e^{i\omega\mu_J - \frac{1}{2}\delta_J^2\omega^2} - 1 - i\omega(\bar{\alpha} - 1) \right) \right),$$

where $\log(\alpha_t) \sim N(\mu_J, \delta_J^2)$ and $\mu_J = \log(\bar{\alpha}) - \frac{1}{2}\delta_J^2$.

Chapter 5

Numerical Results and Benchmarks

The aim of this chapter is to provide the reader with results on the performance of the COS method, both computationally and error-wise, against benchmarks such as Monte Carlo simulations. We will be using the standard Black-Scholes model as the “correct” price for the option, since it is academically accepted as a benchmark in this setting.

5.1 Comparison with Monte Carlo simulation

This comparison uses a Monte Carlo simulation of the terminal stock price under the Black-Scholes model, with $S_0 = 100$, $K = 100$, $r = 0.05$, $q = 0$, $\sigma = 0.20$, and $T = 1$. For each number of paths, the experiment is repeated 30 times. The Monte Carlo price is compared with the COS method applied to the Black-Scholes model with $N = 256$. We can clearly see that at $N = 256$ the COS method outperforms the plain Monte Carlo simulation in absolute error, and for large path counts it is also computationally faster.

Figure 5.1: Black-Scholes call price comparison between Monte Carlo simulation, the closed-form Black-Scholes formula, and the Black-Scholes COS method with $N = 256$.

Monte Carlo paths	Monte Carlo price	95% CI	Closed Black-Scholes	Black-Scholes COS
1,000	10.3602	[9.4469, 11.2736]	10.4506	10.4506
2,500	10.4514	[9.8759, 11.0269]	10.4506	10.4506
5,000	10.3942	[9.9879, 10.8005]	10.4506	10.4506
10,000	10.4707	[10.1821, 10.7593]	10.4506	10.4506
25,000	10.4518	[10.2694, 10.6343]	10.4506	10.4506
50,000	10.4461	[10.3172, 10.5751]	10.4506	10.4506
100,000	10.4565	[10.3651, 10.5478]	10.4506	10.4506
250,000	10.4381	[10.3805, 10.4958]	10.4506	10.4506
500,000	10.4488	[10.4080, 10.4896]	10.4506	10.4506
1,000,000	10.4512	[10.4223, 10.4800]	10.4506	10.4506
2,000,000	10.4529	[10.4325, 10.4733]	10.4506	10.4506

Table 5.1: Data used in Figure 5.1.

We can clearly see that the Monte Carlo confidence interval becomes tighter when the number of paths grows, while the Black-Scholes COS price remains at the closed Black-Scholes benchmark.

Figure 5.2: Monte Carlo root mean squared error against the closed-form Black-Scholes price, compared with the Black-Scholes COS error.

Paths	Monte Carlo RMSE	$\log_{10}(\text{MC RMSE})$	Black-Scholes COS error	$\log_{10}(\text{COS error})$
1,000	0.4900	-0.3098	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
2,500	0.3404	-0.4681	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
5,000	0.2154	-0.6667	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
10,000	0.1451	-0.8382	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
25,000	0.0629	-1.2015	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
50,000	0.0747	-1.1269	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
100,000	0.0458	-1.3391	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
250,000	0.0348	-1.4580	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
500,000	0.0173	-1.7628	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
1,000,000	0.0132	-1.8793	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000
2,000,000	0.0101	-1.9976	< 10^{-14}	-14.0000

Table 5.2: Data used in Figure 5.2.

The data show that the Monte Carlo RMSE decreases with more paths, while the Black-Scholes COS error stays below 10^{-14} in this experiment.

5.2 Comparison with Black-Scholes model

In this section we will compare the plain Black-Scholes model to its COS method computation. We will use $S_0 = 100$, $r = 0.10$, $q = 0$, volatility $\sigma = 0.25$, $T = 0.10$, and strikes between $K = 50$ and $K = 150$. For the convergence plot we show the errors for $K = 80$, $K = 100$, and $K = 120$.

Figure 5.3: Error convergence of the Black-Scholes COS method for the strikes $K = 80$, $K = 100$, and $K = 120$.

N	Error, $K = 80$	Error, $K = 100$	Error, $K = 120$	N	Error, $K = 80$	Error, $K = 100$	Error, $K = 120$
4	1.2602e+00	2.0012e+00	1.2030e+00	64	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
6	3.5831e-01	1.1222e+00	5.7057e-01	96	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
8	2.1564e-01	3.0269e-01	4.4280e-01	128	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
10	4.8393e-02	1.8070e-01	8.2148e-02	192	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
12	2.0422e-02	4.6701e-02	2.2030e-02	256	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
16	5.2255e-04	5.9143e-03	5.8146e-03	384	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
24	9.2292e-06	4.0143e-05	5.9823e-05	512	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
32	9.1396e-08	7.1670e-08	1.7646e-09	768	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14
48	1.4211e-14	1.4211e-14	4.4409e-15	1024	0.0000e+00	1.4211e-14	1.8652e-14

Table 5.3: Data used in Figure 5.3.

We see that increasing N reduces the Black-Scholes COS error very quickly, reaching numerical precision with a relatively low number of terms.

Figure 5.4: Computational cost of the Black-Scholes COS method and the closed-form Black-Scholes formula.

N	COS runtime (ms)	Closed runtime (ms)	N	COS runtime (ms)	Closed runtime (ms)
4	0.0299	0.0100	64	0.0340	0.0100
6	0.0304	0.0100	96	0.0355	0.0100
8	0.0305	0.0100	128	0.0385	0.0100
10	0.0307	0.0100	192	0.0425	0.0100
12	0.0309	0.0100	256	0.0467	0.0100
16	0.0337	0.0100	384	0.0538	0.0100
24	0.0318	0.0100	512	0.0635	0.0100
32	0.0318	0.0100	768	0.0780	0.0100
48	0.0322	0.0100	1024	0.0909	0.0100

Table 5.4: Data used in Figure 5.4.

This table shows that the closed Black-Scholes formula is faster, while the COS runtime grows with N because the finite cosine sum has more terms.

5.3 Heston and Bates models: impact of jumps on prices

Lastly, we will see the data that we get when applying the COS method to the Heston and Bates models. We see here that, as expected, the COS method reduces the error exponentially with a higher N . We also take a look at the fact that the Bates model, computed using the COS method, is very similar to the Heston model when the jumps are lower.

Figure 5.5: Error convergence of the Heston COS method, measured as the maximum absolute error over 51 strikes.

N	Maximum absolute error	N	Maximum absolute error
16	4.4567e-01	24	1.1203e-01
32	3.6052e-02	48	5.0565e-03
64	8.1600e-04	96	2.8387e-05
128	1.0050e-06	192	2.3363e-09
256	5.5564e-12	384	2.8422e-14
512	0.0000e+00	768	2.8422e-14
1024	0.0000e+00		

Table 5.5: Data used in Figure 5.5.

We see here that, as expected, increasing N reduces the Heston COS error exponentially until it reaches numerical precision.

Figure 5.6: Heston COS and Bates COS call prices for low, medium, and high jump-intensity scenarios.

Strike K	Heston COS	Bates COS low	Bates COS medium	Bates COS high
50	50.0705	50.0747	50.1107	50.1732
60	40.2088	40.2226	40.3397	40.5239
70	30.5332	30.5744	30.8890	31.3180
80	21.2366	21.3438	22.0500	22.8651
90	12.7095	12.9317	14.2312	15.5205
100	5.7851	6.1025	7.9127	9.5997
110	1.7871	2.0379	3.6350	5.3162
120	0.4828	0.6086	1.5307	2.7246
130	0.1476	0.2034	0.6729	1.3980
140	0.0514	0.0753	0.3070	0.7293
150	0.0197	0.0299	0.1436	0.3856

Table 5.6: Selected data points from Figure 5.6.

The data show that the Bates COS prices are very similar to the Heston COS price when the jumps are low, and move away as jumps increase.

Figure 5.7: Price difference between the Bates COS model and the Heston COS model for the three jump-intensity scenarios.

Strike K	Low jumps	Medium jumps	High jumps
50	0.0042	0.0402	0.1027
60	0.0139	0.1309	0.3151
70	0.0411	0.3558	0.7847
80	0.1072	0.8134	1.6285
90	0.2223	1.5217	2.8110
100	0.3174	2.1276	3.8146
110	0.2508	1.8479	3.5291
120	0.1258	1.0479	2.2418
130	0.0559	0.5253	1.2504
140	0.0239	0.2556	0.6779
150	0.0101	0.1239	0.3659

Table 5.7: Selected data points from Figure 5.7.

We can clearly see that the difference against Heston is smallest for low jumps and largest for high jumps, especially around the central strikes.

5.4 Accuracy and computational cost analysis

Figure 5.8: Accuracy and computational cost comparison for the Black-Scholes COS method, the Heston COS method, and Black-Scholes Monte Carlo simulation.

Experiment	Accuracy metric	Best error	Work size	Runtime (ms)
Black-Scholes COS	Maximum absolute error over 101 strikes	1.8590e-07	32	0.0318
Heston COS	Maximum absolute error over 51 strikes	2.3363e-09	192	0.0921
Black-Scholes Monte Carlo	RMSE against closed formula	1.0056e-02	2,000,000	22.1344

Table 5.8: Data used in Figure 5.8.

This table summarizes the same comparison: COS reaches much smaller errors with a much smaller work size than the plain Monte Carlo benchmark.

Conclusions

Through this project we have seen a clear path to understanding and implementing the COS method as a numerical method to compute option pricing. It has shown itself to be a clear winner against benchmarks in terms of computation and precision.

Starting from the financial setting, we first introduced the market assumptions that make option pricing meaningful, and then moved towards Fourier methods as a natural way to use the characteristic function of a model. This was important because the COS method is not just a numerical trick, but a method that connects the probabilistic model, the payoff, and the final price in a very direct way.

The numerical results also make the point clear. In the Black-Scholes case, where we can compare against the closed formula, the COS method reaches very small errors with a low number of terms. Against Monte Carlo, the difference is even clearer: Monte Carlo needs a very large number of paths to reduce the error, while the COS method reaches high accuracy much faster. Finally, the Heston and Bates examples show why this method is useful beyond the simplest model, since it can price options efficiently once the characteristic function is known.

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